

An assessment of technology readiness in using several accounting software of undergraduate accounting students in selected schools in Cavite

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the technology readiness in using several accounting software of undergraduate accounting students in selected schools in Cavite. The study determined the levels of the respondents in terms of optimism, innovativeness, discomfort, and insecurity and whether there are significant differences when they are grouped according to gender, age, school, year level, and course. The researchers gathered data from 248 third- and fourth-year BS in Accountancy and BS in Management Accounting students from De La Salle University – Dasmariñas, Imus Institute of Science and Technology, Lyceum of Philippines University – Cavite, and St. Dominic College of Asia. The statistical treatments used for the study were frequency and percentage distribution in analyzing the demographics of the respondents; weighted mean for determining the levels of optimism, innovativeness, discomfort, and insecurity; Independent Samples T-Test for comparison of means of two populations such as gender, year level, and course; One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for measuring significant difference between multiple factors which was used in age and school. Ranking was used on optimism, innovativeness, discomfort, and insecurity that is relative to its overall weighted mean per variable. Based on the weighted mean computation of the four Technology Readiness Index (TRI) variables, only optimism stood out the most. All respondents have an average level of innovativeness. However, there were significant differences in discomfort and insecurity levels when they were grouped according to schools. Respondents from the four schools all have a high level of optimism with no significant difference in responses based on ANOVA. Additionally, there were no significant differences in their responses when they were grouped according to age and year level. However, it was also revealed that there is an average level of discomfort on male and female, but male respondents generally feel more discomfort than females. Along with that, there was also an average level of insecurity for BS Management Accounting respondents compared to BS Accountancy respondents, but the former has higher level of insecurity compared to the latter. Future researchers should apply the Technology Readiness Index to different schools in Cavite or in other settings in the future to see if there are changes in the levels and to determine the significant differences based on demographics.

Keywords: Assessment; Technology readiness; Accounting software; Undergraduate accounting students; School.

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Introduction

Technology has made significant advancements in every area of the business domain, especially in the field of accounting. One of the significant developments of technology in the accounting industry is the

use of accounting software as a means of a new platform for analyzing and interpreting data more efficiently and effectively. Today the usage of this software is widely exercised and has become an everyday routine for many accountants, in which financial transactions can no longer be carried out successfully without the use & knowledge of accounting software (Al-Khaffaf et al., 2018).

According to Florida Tech (2016), as technology advances, the demand for new accounting graduates with combined educational skills and technological readiness in accounting software continues to increase. Parasuraman and Colby (2014) defined technology readiness as the inclination or tendency of people to embrace and use modern technology to achieve home and work objectives. It refers to a set of technological attitudes that together determine the proclivity of accounting students to accept new technologies, such as accounting software, to achieve their work-life preparation goals.

Accounting software, i.e., QuickBooks, Xero, etc., is one of today's most popular software systems utilized widely in the accounting sector (Willis College, 2019). Acquiring knowledge about this software can help accountancy students prepare themselves for the professional world. However, due to the lack of practical accounting skills, some undergraduate students today never got an opportunity to acquire real-time experience using this software prior to their graduation, which questioned their state of technology readiness to use these platforms.

Cloud accounting emerged from cloud computing mixed with accounting software activities (Dimitriu & Matei, 2014). It works through Cloud Service Providers (CSP) and functions the same as the accounting software used by the client. There are a lot of cloud accounting solutions, such as NetSuite, Microsoft Office 365, Xero, MYOB, and QuickBooks Online. However, not everyone is aware of such online accounting software.

The study aims to answer the gap in local literature about technology readiness in using several accounting software programs of undergraduate accounting students. Based on an article issued by Parasuraman and Colby (2014), 127 researchers around the world have been given licenses to use their instruments. Only 4% of the said researchers are from the Philippines. This makes the study of technology readiness in our local literature quite limited, and the researchers wanted to contribute to the growth of this study (Arcega et al., 2015; Caraan et al., 2021).

Statement of the Problem

The general aim of the study is to determine the technology readiness in using several accounting software of undergraduate accounting students in selected schools in Cavite. This study intends to answer the following problems:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Gender
 - 1.2 Age
 - 1.3 School
 - 1.4 Year Level
 - 1.5 Course
2. What is the respondents' evaluation and assessment of their technology readiness in using several accounting software of selected schools in Cavite based on the four variables:
 - 2.1 Optimism
 - 2.2 Innovativeness
 - 2.3 Discomfort
 - 2.4 Insecurity
3. Is there a significant difference in the respondent's evaluation and assessment of their technology readiness in using several accounting software when they are grouped according to demographics?

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the respondents' assessments in the technology readiness of undergraduate accounting students from selected schools in Cavite in using several accounting software under its four dimensions: Optimism, Innovativeness, Discomfort, and Insecurity when they are grouped according to demographics.

Theoretical Framework

This framework of the study aimed to determine the technological readiness of undergraduate students from selected schools in Cavite. This is based on the Technology Readiness Index made by Parasuraman and Colby (2014) which involves four variables namely: optimism, innovativeness, discomfort, and insecurity. The “motivators” of technology readiness are optimism and innovativeness, while the “inhibitors” of technology readiness are discomfort and insecurity.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm of the Study

Methodology

Research Design

In conducting this study, the researchers used a quantitative research method as they deemed it suitable for the study. Descriptive research was used as the research design, which Rubin and Babbie (2016) defines as a method that describes the characteristics of the population under study where data collected from the respondents at one point in time focuses on answering questions of the “what” of the research subject.

The researchers used this method for this study as it poses significance in collecting better investigative results relating to students' technology readiness in using several accounting software. This study used two variables – the demographic profile of the respondents and the Technology Readiness Index (Parasuraman & Colby, 2014). The independent variables in this study are gender, age, year level, school, and course which comprise the demographic profile of the respondents. The technology readiness index is the dependent variable which is subdivided into two such as motivators and inhibitors; under the motivators are optimism and innovativeness, and on the other hand, under the inhibitors are discomfort and insecurity.

Through this study, the researchers will explore the connection between independent and dependent variables.

Sample

The study's respondents were the selected third and fourth-year accountancy students at selected schools in Cavite. The respondents were composed of male and female students of different ages, year levels, gender, name of the school, and course. These students possess the necessary information and knowledge to respond to the questions given in this study. Participants in the study were limited to third- and fourth-year accountancy students because these students already have a broad and well-established understanding of accounting concepts, which will aid in determining their technology readiness for utilizing several accounting software.

Since the researchers were not permitted to obtain the names of all enrolled accountancy students, but only the statistics, due to their confidentiality and privacy, the researchers decided to employ the convenience sampling technique, also known as availability sampling, in which they chose students that were easiest to reach if they passed the criteria in selecting the respondents. The convenience sampling method is defined by Etikan et al. (2015) as a non-random sampling technique where anyone who meets the criteria, such as accessibility or availability and/or the willingness to participate in the study, is considered a participant of the study. In convenience sampling, the researchers selected 62 respondents per school (a total of 248 students), composed of students from different accounting programs such as BS Accountancy and BS Management Accounting in St. Dominic College of Asia, De La Salle University-Dasmariñas, Imus Institute of Science and Technology, and Lyceum of the Philippines University-Cavite Campus. To validate the respondents, the following criteria must be followed: (1) the students must be enrolled in one of the schools listed above; (2) they must be enrolled in one of the following degree programs that are mentioned above; and lastly, (3) the participants must be third and fourth-year students. Respondents were limited to the following third- and fourth-year accountancy students, as these students already possess a broad and well-established understanding of accounting concepts, which will aid in determining their technology readiness for utilizing accounting software.

To get the sample size of the research, the researchers acquired statistics on the population for each of the schools from various accounting programs. De La Salle University—Dasmariñas has a total of 217 students enrolled in different accounting programs, wherein 130 of those are third-year students and 87 of those are fourth-year students. Meanwhile, Lyceum of the Philippines - Cavite has a total enrolment in different accounting programs of 242, with 147 third-year students and 143 fourth-year students. Imus Institute of Science and Technology has a total enrollment of 68 students, 32 of whom are third-year students and 36 of whom are fourth-year students. Lastly, St. Dominic College of Asia has a total of 72 accounting students, with 42 third-year students and 30 fourth-year students. Overall, it has a total population of 647 accounting students, and the researchers selected 62 respondents per school based on the computation of the sample size to avoid bias. A survey was carried out to gather information. A questionnaire was utilized to determine the technology readiness of undergraduate accountancy students in using several accounting software. The questionnaire utilized Likert-type questions and was completed by undergraduate accounting students in selected schools in Cavite. The researchers determined the sample size using Slovin's Formula $[n/1+N(e)^2]$.

Instruments

The research instrument was based on the Technology Readiness Index 2.0 given by Parasuraman and Colby (2014). The researchers have asked for permission to duplicate the questionnaire for this study only but tweaked a few wordings to fit according to the context of the study and to accommodate the variable, several accounting software. Each dimension was measured through four questions per dimension,

thus a total of 16 questions. The questionnaires were distributed through Google Forms, and it was divided into two parts. The first part is the demographic profile of the respondents. It includes age, gender, year level, name of the school, and course. The second part of the questionnaire assessed the technology readiness of the respondents. In Table 1, the Likert scale used to assess the technology readiness of the respondents has an assigned numerical value per category, such as very high, which is equal to 5; high, 4; average, 3; low, 2; and very low, 1.

Table 1. Technology Readiness Index

Range	Weighted Mean	Characteristics	Verbal Interpretation
5	5.00 - 4.21	Strongly Agree	Very High
4	4.20 - 3.41	Agree	High
3	3.40 - 2.60	Neutral	Average
2	2.59 - 1.80	Disagree	Low
1	1.79 - 1.00	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Data Collection

The researchers adopted a standard research protocol in gathering the demanded data in the study. Acknowledging the current situation where face-to-face interaction is highly discouraged, the researchers came up with an online survey questionnaire through Google Forms. The researchers reached out to registrars of different schools by sending a formal email requesting the necessary statistics of the respondents, who are the third- and fourth-year BS Accountancy and BS Management Accounting students, by which schools then responded and sent a PDF file of the said statistics. For Lyceum of the Philippines University Cavite Campus, after researchers did not receive a reply, they reached out instead to the school's Accountancy and Management Accounting organization. For Imus Institute of Technology, researchers personally visited the school's Vice President of Academic Affairs and were asked for some information about the ongoing research paper.

It is difficult to randomize the respondents, so the researchers used the convenience sampling technique to reach out to respondents who were easily accessible. The researchers proceeded with the distribution of the survey questionnaire link that was sent individually through Facebook Messenger for immediate feedback. Consent forms were readily included in the survey questionnaire to assure the respondents of their data privacy. The researchers then monitored the submissions sent by the respondents through the Google form to ensure the progress and observed how many respondents were still needed to achieve the necessary number of responses.

Data Analysis

For data analysis, the study employed descriptive statistics to describe and summarize the connection between variables. The study used graphs, charts, tables, and interpretations to display the collected data in a reasonable and easily comprehensible format. Following the collection of data through the survey questionnaire, the researchers collated, categorized, arranged, and tallied the information gathered. The scoring, the distribution of percentages, and the ranking of the data were all part of the treatment. There were a variety of statistical methods and technologies employed, including frequency and percentage to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, year level, accounting degree, and level of knowledge in using several types of accounting software, weighted means to assess the level of technology readiness, independent samples t-test to determine if there is significant difference in the respondents' assessments on the technology readiness and its variables when they are grouped according to gender, ranking to determine the degree between a set of items, and one-way analysis of variance to measure significant differences between multiple factors used in age and school.

Results and Discussion

Table 2. Demographic Profile of the Respondents (n=248)

Category	Variables	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	63	25.4
	Female	185	74.6
Age	18 – 20 years old	29	11.7
	21 – 23 years old	210	84.7
	24 – 26 years old	5	2.0
	27 – 29 years old	2	0.8
	30 and above	2	0.8
School	De La Salle University – Dasmariñas	62	25
	Imus Institute of Science and Technology	62	25
	Lyceum of the Philippines University – Cavite Campus	62	25
	St. Dominic College of Asia	62	25
Year Level	3rd year	97	39.1
	4th year	151	60.9
Course	BS Accountancy	204	82.3
	BS Management Accounting	44	17.7

Table 2 reveals the demographic profile of the respondents. In terms of age, the table reveals that 185 of the respondents were female, which accounts for 74.6% of the total population, while 63 of the respondents, which accounts for 25.4%, were male. This table demonstrates that based on the population from each of the schools and colleges, the accounting program is proudly dominated by female students. This explains why women are so enthusiastic about learning accounting, not just as a course but also for the technical aspects of the field in its entirety.

In terms of age, the group of undergraduate accounting students whose age range from 21 to 23 years old accounted for 210 of the total responses, which corresponds to an 84.7 percent response rate. This is followed by individuals between the ages of 18 and 20 years old with 29 responses, representing 11.7 percent of the total responses. On the other hand, 5 responses, or 2% were aged 24–26 years old, and finally, the age group that included both 27–29 years old and 30 years old and above received the same frequency of 2 responses, or 0.8% each. Students who are enrolled in the undergraduate accounting programs at the various institutions and colleges are all in their young adult years. Guarantee that most of these respondents are still in college or other types of higher education institutions, it is indeed a fair indication that most of them are between the ages of 21 and 23 years old.

In school, researchers need to survey a minimum of 62 respondents from each school and college to avoid being biased toward a school whose students will answer the survey at an excessively high rate. This indicates that the assessment of technology readiness of undergraduate accounting students is conducted in a fair manner, as all institutions and colleges are given an equal opportunity to respond to the survey to minimize bias and produce an accurate outcome.

In terms of year level, 151 respondents, or 60.9 percent, originated from undergraduate accounting students in their fourth year, and 97 respondents, or 39.1 percent, came from students in their third year. Since the researchers were unable to acquire a list of student names enrolled in their program from each school, due to privacy and confidentiality, the researchers used a sampling method known as convenience sampling. In this method, the researchers only polled students who knew they would have easy access to the survey. This indicates that fourth-year accounting students are the most willing to participate in this study.

In terms of course, most responses came from undergraduate students who are currently enrolled in a BS Accountancy program. This group accounted for at least 204 responses, which is equivalent to 82.3 percent of the total. Undergraduate students majoring in BS Management Accounting only accumulated at

least 44 responses, making up 17.7 percent of the total. This table makes it quite evident that the BS Accountancy program at these four colleges is very well received and that the schools actively promote the program. Although it is known that out of four colleges, only two of them offer a Bachelor of Science in Management Accounting degree, which shows that there are still students enrolled in the program.

Table 3. Respondents' Evaluation and Assessment of their Technology Readiness in using Accounting Software in terms of their Optimism

	Optimism	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
1.	New technologies such as accounting software systems contribute to a better quality of life.	4.62	1	Very High
2.	Technologies such as accounting software systems give me more freedom of mobility.	4.31	2	Very High
3.	Technologies such as accounting software systems give more people control over their daily lives.	4.10	3	High
4.	Technologies such as accounting software systems make me more productive in my personal life.	4.10	3	High
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN		4.28		Very High

Table 3 shows the respondents' evaluation and assessment of their technology readiness in using accounting software in terms of their optimism. The table reveals that most respondents have high levels of optimism. In comparison with the overall weighted mean of the other three variables, optimism garnered the highest overall weighted mean, which means that respondents are considered optimists. In this variable, the lowest weighted mean based on ranking is 4.10, which states that "technologies such as accounting software systems give more people control over their daily lives." This means that most of the respondents agree that technologies such as accounting software give them more control over their lives. Another statement which has the same weighted mean and ranking at 4.10 is "technologies such as accounting software systems make me more productive in my personal life."

The highest weighted mean based on ranking is 4.62, which states that "new technologies such as accounting software systems contribute to a better quality of life." This further proves the results from the study of Odlum (2016) stating that those who have actual practice have a lower optimistic level. Most accounting students only have a strong background in accounting, but not everyone is experienced in using the software itself, thus further fueling the optimism level of the respondents.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluation and Assessment of their Technology Readiness in using Accounting Software in terms of their Innovativeness

	Innovativeness	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
1.	Other people come to me for advice on new technologies such as accounting software systems.	3.08	3	Average
2.	I was one of the first in my circle of friends to acquire new technologies such as accounting software systems when it appeared.	2.67	4	Average
3.	I can usually figure out new high-tech products and services without help from others.	3.36	2	Average
4.	I keep up with the latest technological developments in my areas of interest.	3.69	1	High
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN		3.20		Average

Table 4 shows the respondents' evaluation and assessment of their technology readiness in using accounting software in terms of their innovativeness. The table above shows that the respondents only have an average level of innovativeness with an overall weighted mean of 3.20. This means many respondents may tend to be pioneers and leaders in the field of technology. Considering that most respondents have not yet used an accounting software system, this strengthens the result of the study from Na et al. (2021). Since not everyone has used an accounting software system yet, the level of innovativeness is neither high nor low. This may be contrary to the study by Odium (2016) in the preceding table stating that when respondents do not have experience in using it in practice yet, they may have high optimism. This shows that it is possible for accounting students to be optimistic despite not using the accounting software yet as opposed to the results by Na et al. (2021) that actual users of kiosks mean high optimism.

Table 5. Respondents' Evaluation and Assessment of their Technology Readiness in using Accounting Software in terms of their Discomfort

	Discomfort	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
1.	When I get technical support from a high-tech product or service such as accounting software systems, I feel as if I am being taken advantage of by someone who knows more than I do.	2.41	3	Low
2.	Technical support lines such as accounting software systems are not helpful because they do not explain things in terms I understand.	2.25	4	Low
3.	Sometimes I think that technology systems (such as accounting software systems) are not designed for use by ordinary people.	3.23	1	Average
4.	There is no such thing as a manual for accounting software systems that is written in plain language.	2.98	2	Average
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN		2.72		Average

Table 5 shows the respondents' evaluation and assessment of their technology readiness in using accounting software in terms of their discomfort. It shows that the respondents' discomfort level is average. It has a weighted mean of 2.72, which is the lowest among the four variables in terms of overall weighted mean. This means that respondents may feel that they lack control or are overwhelmed by technology. The highest weighted mean in this variable according to ranking is 3.23 and states that "Sometimes I think that technology systems (such as accounting software systems) are not designed for use by ordinary people." This means that respondents may feel like technologies such as accounting software must only be used by trained people due to its complexity. The lowest weighted mean is 2.25, stating "technical support lines such as accounting software systems are not helpful because they do not explain things in terms I understand." Most respondents may have disagreed with this statement because they think that technical support lines are helpful. The study by Na et al. (2021) revealed that there is a low use intention when there is high discomfort among the respondents. Since the result of discomfort shows an average level, accounting students have an average use intention of accounting software system.

Table 6 shows the respondents' evaluation and assessment of their technology readiness in using accounting software in terms of their insecurity. It shows that the overall weighted mean for insecurity is 3.22, which makes it the second highest variable in terms of overall weighted mean. Respondents have an average level of insecurity, and this means some of them feel that technologies such as accounting software can be harmful to them and may breach their security/personal data.

The statement "Too much technology distracts people to a point that is harmful" garnered the highest means based on ranking with 3.48, which means that most of the respondents agree that technology can be distracting and harmful. The lowest mean is 2.95, with the statement "I do not feel confident doing business with a place that can only be reached online." This implies that, because cloud accounting software

can only be accessed or utilized online, respondents believe that it should not be the exclusive resource used when dealing with business processes. Because it also demonstrates that excessive use of technology, such as accounting software, can be a source of distraction because this software deals with any browsing habits that other people may navigate.

Table 6. Respondents' Evaluation and Assessment of their Technology Readiness in using Accounting Software in terms of their Insecurity

	Insecurity	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
1.	People are too dependent on technologies like accounting software systems to do things for them.	3.41	2	High
2.	Too much technology distracts people to a point that is harmful.	3.48	1	High
3.	Technology such as accounting software systems lowers the quality of relationships by reducing personal interaction.	3.04	3	Average
4.	I do not feel confident doing business with a place that can only be reached online.	2.95	4	Average
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN		3.22		Average

A study by Blut and Wang (2019) states that there is a negative relationship between insecurity trait and technology usage. This means that when technology usage is high, insecurity traits are low and vice versa. The results disprove this because although most respondents do not use accounting software, the insecurity trait is not that high but average.

Table 7. Significant Difference on Respondents' Evaluation and Assessment of their Technology Readiness in using Accounting Software when Grouped According to Gender

TR	Gender	Mean	T	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Optimism	Male	4.26	-0.47	0.28	Accept	Not Significant
	Female	4.29				
Innovativeness	Male	3.19	-0.07	0.33	Accept	Not Significant
	Female	3.20				
Discomfort	Male	2.84	1.62	0.01	Reject	Significant
	Female	2.68				
Insecurity	Male	3.19	-0.32	0.90	Accept	Not Significant
	Female	3.23				

Table 7 shows the significant difference in the respondents' evaluation and assessment of technology readiness in using various accounting software when grouped according to gender. Based on the table, there were no significant differences in the three variables namely optimism ($t = -0.47$, $p = 0.28$), innovativeness ($t = -0.07$, $p = 0.33$), and insecurity ($t = -0.32$, $p = 0.90$). Since the p-values of the said variables were greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Surprisingly, in the variable discomfort, there was a significant difference ($t = 1.62$, $p = 0.01$) between male and female. Since the p-value for the said variables were less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. Male respondents were deemed to have a higher mean with 2.84 as opposed to female with 2.68, though both have a verbal interpretation of "average." This suggests that males generally feel more discomfort in using accounting software systems compared to females.

This contradicts the study by MacNevin et al. (2021) and Na et al. (2021) suggesting that men were more likely to be more technology ready than women. The study of Badri et al. (2013) also confirmed that there is a significant difference between males and females and that male respondents have higher scores in optimism, innovativeness, and insecurity compared to female respondents. There is no significant difference in terms of discomfort levels in this study.

Based on this study, male accounting students do not really have a significant difference with female accounting students in terms of technology readiness except for discomfort. Interestingly, the study suggests that male accounting students have higher discomfort levels in using accounting software compared to female accounting students.

Table 8. Significant Difference in Respondents' Evaluation and Assessment of their Technology Readiness in using Accounting Software when Grouped According to Age

TR	Age	Mean	T	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Optimism	18 – 20 years old	4.44	1.00	0.41	Accept	Not Significant
	21 – 23 years old	4.27				
	24 – 26 years old	4.30				
	27 – 29 years old	4.00				
	30 yrs. old and above	4.13				
Innovativeness	18 – 20 years old	3.22	0.46	0.77	Accept	Not Significant
	21 – 23 years old	3.19				
	24 – 26 years old	3.50				
	27 – 29 years old	3.50				
	30 yrs. old and above	3.13				
Discomfort	18 – 20 years old	2.61	0.65	0.62	Accept	Not Significant
	21 – 23 years old	2.72				
	24 – 26 years old	2.85				
	27 – 29 years old	3.38				
	30 yrs. old and above	2.63				
Insecurity	18 – 20 years old	3.06	1.13	0.34	Accept	Not Significant
	21 – 23 years old	3.23				
	24 – 26 years old	3.40				
	27 – 29 years old	4.00				
	30 yrs. old and above	3.63				

Table 8 shows the significant difference in the respondents' evaluation and assessment of technology readiness in using various accounting software when grouped according to age. Based on the results, there are no significant differences in the variables such as optimism ($f = 1.00$, $p = 0.41$), innovativeness ($f = 0.46$, $p = 0.77$), discomfort ($f = 0.65$, $p = 0.62$), and insecurity ($f = 1.13$, $p = 0.34$). This means that regardless of age, the responses of respondents were almost the same for every variable. Since the p-values of the said variables were greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Table 9 explains the significant difference in the respondents' evaluation and assessment of technology readiness in using various accounting software when grouped according to school. For optimism ($f = 1.09$, $p = 0.35$) and innovativeness ($f = 1.63$, $p = 0.18$), there were no significant differences in four schools. Since the p-values of the said variables were greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted. Interestingly, there was a significant difference in discomfort ($f = 3.68$, $p = 0.01$) and insecurity ($f = 4.28$, $p = 0.01$). Since the p-values for the said variables were less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Although all schools were proven to be highly optimistic, there were differences with their responses in discomfort and insecurity variables. St. Dominic College of Asia has a mean of 2.88 and Lyceum of the Philippines University – Cavite has a mean of 2.85 and they have the highest and second highest mean in discomfort, respectively. Students from both schools have average levels of discomfort. De La Salle University – Dasmariñas has a mean of 2.59 in which students have possess low level of discomfort. On the other hand, Imus Institute of Science and Technology has a mean of 2.56, which students possess low level of discomfort too. Meanwhile, St. Dominic College of Asia has a mean of 3.44, implying that students have high level of insecurity. Additionally, Imus Institute of Science and Technology has a mean of 3.24 or an average level of insecurity. Lastly, Lyceum of the Philippines University – Cavite and De La Salle University – Dasmariñas have means of 3.22 and 2.98, respectively, which share an average level of insecurity.

Table 9. Significant Difference in Respondents' Evaluation and Assessment of their Technology Readiness in using Accounting Software when Grouped According to School

TR	Age	Mean	T	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Optimism	DLSU-D	4.24	1.09	0.35	Accept	Not Significant
	IIST	4.35				
	LPU-C	4.33				
	SDCA	4.21				
Innovativeness	DLSU-D	3.17	1.63	0.18	Accept	Not Significant
	IIST	3.29				
	LPU-C	3.27				
	SDCA	2.59				
Discomfort	DLSU-D	2.56	3.68	0.01	Reject	Significant
	IIST	2.85				
	LPU-C	2.88				
	SDCA	2.98				
Insecurity	DLSU-D	3.24	4.28	0.01	Reject	Significant
	IIST	3.22				
	LPU-C	3.44				
	SDCA	4.24				

Table 10. Significant Difference in Respondents' Evaluation and Assessment of their Technology Readiness in using Accounting Software when Grouped According to Year Level

TR	Year Level	Mean	T	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Optimism	3rd Year	4.31	0.60	0.31	Accept	Not Significant
	4th Year	4.27				
Innovativeness	3rd Year	3.15	-0.93	0.94	Accept	Not Significant
	4th Year	3.23				
Discomfort	3rd Year	2.67	-0.90	0.54	Accept	Not Significant
	4th Year	2.75				
Insecurity	3rd Year	3.30	1.40	0.35	Accept	Not Significant
	4th Year	3.17				

Furthermore, Table 13 shows the significant difference in the respondents' evaluation and assessment of technology readiness in using various accounting software when grouped according to year level. The table below shows that there are no significant differences in optimism ($t = 0.60$, $p = 0.31$), innovativeness ($t = -0.93$, $p = 0.94$), discomfort ($t = -0.90$, $p = 0.54$), and insecurity ($t = 1.40$, $p = 0.35$). This implies that when the respondents were grouped according to their year level, their responses on the four variables were statistically just the same. Since the p-values were greater than 0.05 for the said variables, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Table 14. Significant Difference in Respondents' Evaluation and Assessment of their Technology Readiness in using Accounting Software when Grouped According to Course

TR	Year Level	Mean	T	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Optimism	BS Accountancy	4.27	-0.60	0.35	Accept	Not Significant
	BS Management Accounting	4.32				
Innovativeness	BS Accountancy	3.16	-1.97	0.54	Accept	Not Significant
	BS Management Accounting	3.36				
Discomfort	BS Accountancy	2.70	-0.93	0.71	Accept	Not Significant
	BS Management Accounting	2.81				
Insecurity	BS Accountancy	3.21	-0.41	0.04	Reject	Not Significant
	BS Management Accounting	3.26				

Table 14 shows the significant difference in the respondents' evaluation and assessment of technology readiness in using various accounting software when grouped according to course. For the three variables, optimism ($t = -0.60$, $p = 0.35$), innovativeness ($t = -1.97$, $p = 0.54$), and discomfort ($t = -0.93$, $p = 0.71$) have no significant differences when they are grouped according to course. Since the p-values were greater than 0.05 for the said variables, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that for every variable, responses of the BS Accountancy and BS Management Accounting respondents were similar with each other.

Surprisingly, for insecurity ($t = -0.41$, $p = 0.04$), there was a significant difference in their responses. Since the p-values were less than 0.05 for the said variable, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a difference in the responses of BS Accountancy and BS Management Accounting respondents as to insecurity, with an average verbal interpretation. Although BS Management Accounting respondents have higher mean than the BS Accountancy, it does not necessarily mean that they have high levels of insecurity. It is apparent in the table that BS Accountancy and BS Management Accounting students are both highly optimistic when it comes to using an accounting software system.

Conclusion

This study aims to assess the technology readiness of undergraduate accounting students in select schools in Cavite in using several accounting software based on the four variables, namely, optimism, innovativeness, discomfort, and insecurity. Respondents' profiles reveal that many of them are female undergraduate accounting students enrolled in a bachelor's degree program in accountancy. These students are between the ages of 21 and 23 because they are young adults who are currently enrolled in college or university. To avoid bias and report a fair outcome of the research, researchers obtained the required number of responses for each school to be surveyed.

Based on the respondents' assessment and evaluation of their technological readiness in using various accounting software, students have high level of optimism. Optimism garnered the highest overall weighted mean, in contrast to innovation, discomfort, and insecurity, which all gained a verbal interpretation of "average." With respect to the significant difference of the respondents, there exist no significant findings when grouped by age and year level. However, there are noteworthy findings when grouped according to gender, course, and school, such as discomfort and insecurity.

Recommendations

To accommodate the results driven by the optimist level of students about their technology readiness in using accounting software, which garnered a "Very High" remark, it is appropriate for every school and college to establish a training program that is initiated by its respective academic organization. For instance, each Junior Philippine Institute of Accountants (JPIA) or Junior Philippine Association of Management Accountants (JPAMA)-affiliated organization should require its members to participate in a membership-training program that focuses on learning and utilizing accounting software. Since this study does not propose any changes to the curriculum, a training program initiated by each organization will be the most effective means of educating students on using accounting software effectively. With this training, the organization can cooperate with other organizations or training centers who can accept undergraduates into their training program. Students are encouraged to complete this training so that, prior to graduation, they are competent accounting students with diverse skills and knowledge of accounting software.

To accommodate the findings that led to the lowest rank in innovativeness mean, which earned an "Average" rating, the mentioned training should also contain a thorough analysis of the most recent updates and current accounting industry trends. The training should also include a review of additional accounting

software trends that students may choose to explore further. In this area, students can be innovative in identifying new accounting software that they can share with their classmates and friends.

By adopting technology-focused training programs throughout the undergraduate years, it is possible to decrease discomfort by giving them additional training at the end of every semester or during summer so that it will be progressively easy for them to use and navigate the software. This will help in easing the students' discomfort by using accounting software. Not only that, once they are properly trained, they will be able to share their knowledge with ordinary people. This recommendation is applied to all the respondents of the course, school, and gender regardless of significant differences. This is to ensure that the selected schools will lessen the discomfort levels in the future.

To further lessen the average level of insecurity and address the highest rank in insecurity by the respondents, the researchers recommend that organizations should conduct seminars about productivity and the benefits that accounting software can bring to the students and on how to reduce the use of other technologies such as social media during work and class. With cloud-based accounting software that can be only reached online and may be used during work-from-home setups, it will be easier for accountants/students to be distracted because social media or other online platforms are easily accessible for them. This recommendation is applied to all students regardless of significant differences because the same goal of lessening insecurity level applies to all the schools. Additionally, since there is a significant difference in courses, training courses are specifically addressed to BS Management Accounting and initiated by JPAMA or other related organizations.

Moreover, future researchers should apply the Technology Readiness Index to different schools in Cavite or in other settings. Future researchers do this after the recommendations are applied to see if there are future changes in the levels of optimism, innovativeness, discomfort, and insecurity, as well as if there are significant differences in the respondents based on their demographics.

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